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D2.1: Report on infrared heating panels and enhanced thermal cabin insulation (PU)

Publishable Executive Summary

In the MINDED project the improvements on the battery-electric zero-emission IVECO eDaily minibus will be delivered in order to increase its performance and reliability. Aiming at the real-world improvement, MINDED will show 20 % increase of the driving range under WLTP conditions at 0 °C (in comparison to the baseline version) while reaching the cost reduction by at least 5 % at vehicle level and reducing the development time by 30 % through advanced design tools.

The MINDED project is organized in seven Work Packages (WPs). As a part of the work performed within WP2 - Heating system and thermal user comfort, the focus of this Deliverable 2.1 - Report on infrared heating panels and enhanced thermal cabin insulation, is on the concept for a combined energy reduction of 30 % for heating the passenger cabin with infrared heating panels and enhanced thermal cabin insulation.

In the structure of WP2, Task 2.1 is dealing with the positioning, sizing, and design of infrared heating panels, and Task 2.2 is focused on the design of enhanced thermal cabin insulation. As the outcome from these two tasks, summarized in this deliverable, the qualitative analysis was performed for assessing the potential for saving energy needed for the cabin heating. Regarding the use of infrared panels (Task 2.1) the preparatory work for the installation was completed, and for the applying of the enhanced thermal insulation (Task 2.2) the distribution was elaborated based on the preliminary simulations.

There are three more tasks (Task 2.3 to 2.5) that are complementing the work of WP2. While fulfilling the aims of Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 defined within the WP2, there were no time delays or plan deviations related to this Deliverable 2.1.

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Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Nomenclature

Symbol or Shortname	Description
AC	Air Conditioning
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IR	Infrared Radiation
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
SotA	State of the Art
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WLTP	Worldwide-Harmonised Light-Vehicle Test Procedure
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The objective of MINDED project is to deliver a battery-electric, zero-emission IVECO eDaily minibus with 20 % improved driving range under real-world conditions. This is shown by driving the bus under reproducible conditions according to the Worldwide-Harmonised Light-Vehicle Test Procedure (WLTP) at 0 °C at the climatized dynamometer. The objective is reached by introducing a highly efficient heating system for the driver and passengers based on infrared heating panels. The heating panels are controlled by an innovative human-machine interface through which passengers provide feedback on their current thermal comfort. Based on this feedback, a climate control strategy determines the best settings for optimum comfort. An optimal thermal and energy management strategy realises those settings, while minimising the heating system's energy consumption. The performance of the heating system implemented in the IVECO eDaily minibus will be demonstrated on a chassis dynamometer at 0 °C ambient temperature at TRL 7, while the optimised air conditioning system with optimised performance in heat pump mode is demonstrated on the ThermoLab testbed under various operating conditions at TRL 6. This system incorporates an innovative oil-free centrifugal e-compressor with gas bearing technology for increased performance and reduced noise. The targeted TRLs in MINDED are fully consistent with the call's requirement to achieve at least TRL 6 by the end of the project.

To further improve the performance of the IVECO eDaily minibus an overall predictive thermal and energy management strategy will be demonstrated in the Digital Twin Model of the entire vehicle. The model considers the vehicle's powertrain, the implemented infrared heating system, the air conditioning system demonstrated on the testbed and a prediction of the driving behaviour based on artificial intelligence (AI) and Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) sensors.

The ambition of MINDED project involves the development, implementation, and demonstration of technologies at TRL 6-7, demonstrating a 20 % improved range at 0 °C compared to the baseline battery-electric IVECO eDaily minibus. MINDED will furthermore demonstrate cost reduction by at least 5 % at vehicle level, while at the same time increasing the performance and reliability and a reducing the development time by 30 % through digital twin and AI deployment.

Figure 1: MINDED objectives.

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This deliverable deals with the presentation of a concept aiming at a combined energy reduction of 30 % for heating the passenger cabin with infrared heating panels and an improved cabin insulation (Obj. #2).

2 Infrared Heating System

General idea

The aim of this project is to develop an energy-efficient thermal system in combination with the highest possible comfort for passengers in the field of passenger transport. This is an extremely important aspect since, especially in vehicles with electric drive, thermal energy must be supplied by the battery for conditioning the passenger cabin, which has a serious impact on energy consumption and thus on the vehicle’s driving range. It is a well-known fact in the field of vehicle electrification that the range can be reduced by up to 50 % in adverse climatic conditions. In commercial passenger transport, this factor can have even more significant impact, since the SoTA solutions using convective air conditioning of the cabin require the same heating power regardless of whether there are 3 or 19 passengers in the vehicle.

To account for the abovementioned issues, an innovative radiation heating concept based on electrical resistive thin heater layers, named LITEHEAT, will be developed by VIL and integrated into the demonstrator vehicle. The proposed heating technology results in a lightweight and safe cabin heating solution with a high comfort level for the driver and all passengers, and a significantly higher energy efficiency than conventional (purely convective) heating technologies. As the required electrical energy is almost entirely converted to heat, the efficiency of the proposed solution tends to the theoretical maximum of 100 %. Tests with LITEHEAT have shown a reduction in energy consumption of at least 30 % depending on the design and environmental conditions, given that the air temperature within the passenger cabin can be reduced by approximately 5 °C while maintaining the passenger comfort. Reducing the air temperature, in turn, minimises the thermal losses at cold ambient temperatures, increasing thus the overall efficiency of the thermal management system. This contributes directly to AREA I Obj. #5 of 30 % energy reduction. With the thickness of only about 150 µm and the weight of only about 200 g/m², the LITEHEAT technology can be used very flexibly regarding form and shape of the panels. Figure 2 depicts the heating elements integrated e.g. into the seats and on the floor, while the optimum location and configuration of the heating panels will be determined using 3D simulations and subjective comfort tests in the climatic chamber. The heating panels can be attached at many different locations in the passenger cabin in the near field of the passengers (basically without limitation in power density) and can be laid out to achieve heat-up times in the range of only a few seconds. A considerable reduction of the energy demand is guaranteed by the demand-oriented partial heating by means of infrared heating elements. An automatic passenger detection system ensures that only those infrared heating elements are in operation that are required for the thermal conditioning of the occupied seats. The radiation heat emitted by each of the panels is evenly distributed, and hence it is perceived as very comfortable. At the same time, LITEHEAT heater layers are very safe and robust in operation: they are already certified as heated floor panels in Large Passenger Aircraft (Boeing, Airbus) where they must withstand very high stress and mechanical damage without creating dangerous hotspots.

Figure 2: Radiant heating concept with infrared heating panels: front view (a) and side view (b).

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Draft concept

Partner VIL developed a vehicle-specific LITEHEAT heating application based on radiant and convective heat (Figure 3). The LITEHEAT heating applications are designed as full-surface heaters with the heating elements consisting of polymer heater layers developed by VIL, which are characterized by high efficiency, a self-regulating effect as well as high robustness and low weight. Two heater types were considered, for the floor and the seat backrest, with their sizes summarized in Table 2.

Figure 3: Prototype heater element production at VIL.

Table 2: Full face heaters size

Heater type	Dimensions
Floor heaters, 3 pc	450 mm x 250 mm
Floor heaters, 7 pc	450 mm x 350 mm
Floor heaters, 1 pc	570 mm x 450 mm
Floor heaters, 1 pc	620 mm x 350 mm
Floor heaters, 4 pc	620 mm x 450 mm
Floor heaters, 2 pc	560 mm x 340 mm
Floor heaters, 1 pc	500 mm x 350 mm
Seat Backrest, 18 pc	450 mm x 250 mm

LITEHEAT radiant heaters were produced for the seat backrests and designed for an output of 250 W/m² @ 24 V. These heaters provide infrared radiant heat to the passengers sitting behind the respective backrests (Figure 4). A total of 18 of these backrest heaters have been produced, corresponding to the number of backrests available.

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Figure 4: Preparation of IR heating elements for backrest and floor.

In addition, LITEHEAT floor heating panels have been developed which are placed in the foot area of the individual passengers (Figure 5). These heating elements are also designed as full-surface heating with the heating technology developed by VIL with polymer heater layers. The underfloor heating systems emit convective heat to the upper layer and radiant heat upwards. 19 heated floor heating panels were produced with different dimensions in order to be able to integrate them into the geometries corresponding to the vehicle. In addition, a floor heating panel was also produced for the driver. The heat output was also designed for an output of 250 W/m² @ 24 V. The heat output W/m² of all LITEHEAT heating panels may be adjusted either via PWM (Pulse Width Modulation) or via the change of electrical voltage or current.

Figure 5: Production of heating applications.

2.1 Installing infrared heating panels

For the arrangement of the heating panels in the left (double) row, shown in Figure 6, each backrest has one panel installed (i.e. one panel for each passenger) while the floor panels are installed per row (i.e. one panel for two passengers).

Figure 6: Floor and seat backrest heaters in the left (double) passenger row.

Unlike in the left row with the double seats, in the row to the right with the single seats the individual panels are installed for each passenger both on the floor and the backrest (Figure 7). The number of panels installed around a seat will influence the regulation and control options of the entire system.

Figure 7: Floor and seat backrest heaters in the right (single) passenger row.

The heating panels for the driver and the passenger bank in the back of the vehicle (Figure 8) are treated differently, since there the location for the front heaters (backrest) is not available or missing. For the driver

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position, though, the traditional heating can be provided from the air openings. The passenger bank in the back, however, needs a special consideration.

Figure 8: Floor heaters for the driver and the passenger bank.

3 Cabin Insulation

General SotA in vehicle construction is still often based on vehicles with combustion engines, which have an excess of thermal energy available. Integrated leaks in the passenger compartments are designed to remove moisture and odours. Depending on the type of vehicle, up to 60 % of the thermal energy or cooling energy introduced escapes through these leaks.

3.1 Insulation of passenger cabin

General idea

One of the aims of the MINDED project is to realise a (part of the) vehicle interior with improved thermal insulation properties and to directly enhance the thermal insulation capabilities of the passenger compartment and/or the cabin (Figure 9). The thermal insulation of current vehicles is often relatively poor, and this holds especially for minibuses as they need to provide large openings and fenestration surfaces. For example, the doors, roofs, and side-panels consist of poorly insulated steel sheets with high thermal conductivity, causing significant thermal losses which are compensated by HVAC with high energy consumption. Adding the effect of air entrainment, it is clear that minibuses have a very large exchange of thermal energy with the environment.

Figure 9: Schematic qualitative representation of improved thermal insulation of the passenger cabin at 0 °C.

Materials with good insulation properties reduce the thermal losses and hence help to decrease the overall energy consumption for maintaining the passenger thermal comfort. Typically, materials with pronounced

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porous structure guarantee better thermal insulation due to low thermal conductivity. Additionally, they absorb vibrations and noise and therefore they increase passenger ride comfort. Applying such insulating material, the cabin components' noise, and vibration characteristics as well as their thermal performance are significantly improved.

The main goal of this Technology Brick is the development of solutions, including the application of novel materials, to improve the thermal insulation of vehicles and hence reduce the energy consumption needs over a wide range of ambient conditions. An improved cabin insulation reduces the thermal losses from the vehicle cabin via all outside surfaces. This will lead to an estimated reduction of the required energy for the heating/cooling system by approximately 15 to 35 %, depending on the ambient condition. The expected reduction of energy consumption in AREA I from these factors is around 20 % for either heating or cooling through optimised thermal insulation.

Draft concept

For the cabin insulation concept development, the numerical analysis of the fluid flow and heat transfer within the minibus passenger cabin was performed. To this end, the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations have been performed using the OpenFoam CFD library suite. In the focus of this analysis are two cases: heating in winter – the ambient temperature of the surrounding is low and the minibus cabin is supplied with hot air (Figure 10), and cooling in summer – the ambient temperature of the surrounding is high and the minibus cabin is supplied with cold air (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Wall temperature distribution for the heating in winter case, front-top view (left) and back-bottom view (right).

In both cases the seats are heated (resembling the minibus full of passengers), and all air opening supply the air with the same inlet velocity. In the winter case the supply air has 25 °C higher temperature that the surrounding (Figure 10), while in the summer case the supply air is 25 °C lower (Figure 11). Although this setup does not represent any particular operating mode, it is well suited for the concept analysis.

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Figure 11: Wall temperature distribution for the cooling in summer case, front-top view (left) and back-bottom view (right).

As a result of this qualitative numerical study, one can identify the areas where the differences between the wall temperature and the surrounding are the highest. This is the indication of the areas where the wall heat losses will be the highest, and there the applying of the insulation will improve the overall energy efficiency. Discarding the areas which cannot or only partly be modified (glasses), one is left with the top, bottom and back walls which are suitable for increasing the insulation in order to reduce the heat losses.

Regarding the top walls (Figure 12) the aesthetics needs to be considered by the installation of the thermal insulation. Furthermore, the functionality criterion needs to be met, including the arrangement for the air supply openings and the top window.

Figure 12: Top wall of the minibus.

For applying the insulation on the floor (Figure 13) one needs to consider that the finishing has to be walking layer of appropriate material. Furthermore, this needs to be considered together with the heating panel distribution, since floor panels are installed under each passenger seat. This overlapping of applied measures needs to be resolved having in mind both the energy efficiency and the cost efficiency.

Figure 13: Bottom wall of the minibus.

As for the back walls and the side walls (Figure 14), there are distinct features in the minibus design that need to be preserved. Namely, the back wall is foreseen for the door, and at the sides there is a protective layer next to the passengers’ legs.

Figure 14: Back and side walls for potential insulation installation.

3.2 Insulation of heating system

General idea

As the starting point for enhancing the thermal insulation regarding the heating system of the minibus, the analysis of the existing configuration reveals that the functionality of the system was the driving force behind the heating system design – and the system efficiency is clearly going to be the next logical step. Namely, the actual layout of the system aimed at providing the neutral indoor thermal comfort for the passengers. To that purpose, the radiator was installed in the front section of the passenger compartment to ensure the heating operation, while in the rear the AC unit is placed in the corner of the luggage shelf, and it is used for the cooling through the air nozzles above the passengers’ heads and along the luggage shelf (Figure 15). In addition, there is the roof vent that can serve both for the air supply and air extraction.

Figure 15: Minibus passenger cabin with heating system components, radiator (left) and AC unit (right).

While the functionality of the installed heating system can be satisfactory, the focus of the present analysis is on the improvement of its energy efficiency. This aim can be achieved by increasing the thermal insulation of the existing thermal system, considering the entire minibus passenger cabin as a unified system and not a collection of heating and cooling components. In particular, this is related to the minibus surfaces (internal and external), including the windows and heating/cooling elements. As a special requirement in this project, however, the installing options for the heating panels are not to be affected, since they are a specific point of investigation.

Draft concept

For the development of the concept for the insulation of the heating system, the preliminary examination was performed with the thermal image camera. Similarly to the analysis of the numerical results, the aim was to identify the correlation between the areas of higher surface temperatures and the operation of the heating system components.

In the development of the improved heating system design, it is generally worth reconsidering the disposition of the heating system components. However, as an illustrative example of the current energy efficiency improvement potential, there is the uninsulated heating system piping under the passenger cabin with avoidable heat losses which are due to high temperature differences between the heating fluid (about 70 °C) in the piping and the surrounding ambient air, which was 0 °C during this measurement in the climatic chamber (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Thermal image of the uninsulated heating system piping under the passenger cabin.

Another hot-spot indicated by the thermal image camera can be seen in the top corners at the minibus rear, and it is related to the installation of the AC unit on the luggage shelf (Figure 17). This area can be insulated easily and without hindering the heating panel installation, since it is the side wall along the luggage shelf on the top of the cabin.

Figure 17: Thermal image of the top rear wall (left) where AC unit is located (right).

By comparing the left side of the minibus (where the passenger radiator is located) and the right side of the minibus (Figure 18 left and right respectively) one can notice a hot-spot indicating much higher heat exchange with the ambient (higher temperatures) at the radiator location.

Figure 18: Thermal image of the left-side wall where the radiator is located (left) and the right-side wall (right).

On the left side, there is the imprint of the passenger radiator, since a part of the heat is being conducted through the side wall of the minibus. This heat loss can be reduced by applying the insulation material on the wall behind the radiator (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Thermal image of the left-side wall (left) where the radiator is located (right).

On the minibus roof there is the air vent with four openings (Figure 20). This can be used both for supplying the ambient air into the cabin and extracting the cabin air outside. However, this vent is directly connected to the outside environment without any flow treatment. Installing a filter, insulation or a rubber flap which folds away when the fan is turned on might bring some benefits in terms of thermal behaviour.

Figure 20: Minibus roof vent, directly in connection with the ambient air.

For the insulation of windows, not so many appropriate solutions can be found that do not affect the main functionality of windows: to provide light and visual experience to the passengers. One possibility could be an enhancement of the glazing, which would be a costly but very effective method of reducing thermal losses through the windows. Another, much cheaper and quicker method would be the installation of reflection foils, which are commercially available for home windows (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Commercial solution for improving the windows thermal insulation in homes (<https://www.velken.at/p/isolierfolie-leicht-getoent-durchsichtig/>).

For the reflection foils it is claimed that in the cold ambient conditions they can reduce the heat losses in the room by reflecting the infrared radiation. Several issues are likely to occur regarding the practicality of this windows insulation measure, such as mounting and maintaining. Furthermore, its effectiveness is yet to be tested under the operating conditions relevant for the minibus cabins.

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4 Conclusions

This Deliverable 2.1 presents the work on the qualitative analysis of the potential for reducing the energy needed for the cabin heating, by installing the infrared heating panels (Task 2.1) and applying the enhanced thermal cabin insulation (Task 2.2), with the overall goal of 30 % combined energy reduction regarding the heating of the passenger cabin.

Considering the heating system based on the infrared heating panels, all preparatory work for the design and installation is completed. This includes the prototype heater element production, given the size and the disposition of the heaters appropriate for the installation. The positioning of the infrared heating panels was determined based on the surface availability, safety and overall functionality criteria. In order to put the system in operation, one needs to complete the electric energy supply and the control options.

For the improvement of the thermal insulation, several sections have been identified for the optimal placement of the additional insulation. Namely, by means of the thermal images at the locations around the piping of the heating system, behind the AC unit and the passenger radiator the hot-spots are appearing due to the respective operating conditions. Furthermore, from the numerical fluid flow simulations one can observe the increased temperature differences at the cabin roof, floor and the back wall, which is the indication for the increased heat transfer (energy losses).

All the identified sections that are considered for the additional insulation are analysed also from the perspective of the overall functionality. In addition to the locations at the cabin wall which can easily accommodate the additional insulation without any negative implications, there are e.g. the windows which occupy a large area but cannot be easily modified without influencing the main functionality of the windows or at least only with very costly and much heavier solutions.

5 Acknowledgment

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